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PASS: A COMPUTERIZED PREDICTION OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY SPECTRA FOR CHEMICAL SUBSTANCES

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ABSTRACT

PASS is a web-based software tool which is used in the prediction of the biological activity spectrum of biologically active compounds based on their structure. The prediction tool uses the 2D structure of the compounds as the basic input and predicts the activities of even those compounds which are not synthesised and chemically tested yet i.e., only information about their structural formula is available till now. Hence comparing the structure of the input compound with the structures already present in the data base of the software and giving the activity spectrum of the that compound as the output. This makes the prediction of different biological effects of the compound such as pharmacological and toxicological effects of the organic drug molecules at early stages and therefore enabling users to identify potential leads of drugs and reducing development time of drugs in the field of research and development. PASS online is very well accepted by the users for its easy, efficient and time saving qualities, aiding in reduction of failures in the clinical trials and also finding new indications for the old drugs. The pass prediction tool gives the biological activities (including pharmacotherapeutic as well as toxic effects) of the input 2D structure as the result of prediction in the descending order of their probability ratios $P_a:P_i$ (probability to be active : probability to be inactive), hence giving the output list in order of their most useful activities.

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INTRODUCTION

PASS is a computer aided software tool that predicts the biological activity spectrum of different compounds based on their structure. The Prediction result depends on the analysis of structure activity-relationships for more than 250,000 biologically active substances including drugs, drug-substances, leads and toxic substances. Pass works on the principle that the biological activity of a compound equates its structure.

To obtain the expected biological activity profile of the compound solely structural/ molecular formula is necessary, so prediction is possible even for those virtual structures designed in the computer but not synthesized yet. PASS Online has the ability to predict over 4000 different kinds of biological activities that include therapeutic effects, toxic effects, adverse effects, enzyme interaction, mechanism of action etc.

Based on the world's largest known data collections consisting of the biological activities of chemical compounds and their structures, PASS online allow its users to identify and note the potential lead structures out of millions of chemical substances, thereby effortlessly shortening development times for specific drugs or molecular probes for research and analysis. This is one of the most successful programs giving you early indications about your compounds that it might be useful. ^[1]

TERMS USED IN PASS:

The Biological Activity Spectrum of a chemical compound is the collection of various types of biological activities that indicates the output of its interaction with different biological molecules.

Pa (probability "to be active") evaluates the possibility that the predicted compound belongs to the category of active compounds.

Pi (probability "to be inactive") evaluates the possibility that the predicted compound belongs to the category of inactive compounds. ^[2]

ABOUT PASS PROGRAM:

PASS online program is organized by the V.N. Orechovich Institute of biomedical chemistry under the management of the Russian Foundation of Basic Research. The underlying database content of PASS program stores more than 180000 biologically similar compounds and is continuously updated and re-stored. It aids in simultaneous prediction of over 780 pharmacological effects and drug mechanism depending on the 2D structure of the input molecule. The ability of PASS online program for prediction extends to over 3678 pharmacological effects, toxicities and drug mechanisms.

The input form of the chemical substance is its structural formula while the resultant output is the potential biological activities of the substance in the descending order of its p_a (probability to be active). The mean accuracy of prediction results given by PASS is found to be 95%, as stated by LOOCV (leave one out cross validation) and hence finding it reasonable to use PASS Program before initializing research and synthesis phases. ^[3]

SUCCESS OF PASS IN RECENT YEARS:

In the initial months of PASS Internet's usage, from more than 60 countries about 1000 researches have utilised the online program for prediction of about 23,000 different chemical substances. In the NCI database, information about more than 64 million PASS predictions for almost 250,000 different compounds is available on its website. From these predictions, selection of compounds with desirable and without undesirable biological activities can be easily done for further screening purposes. ^[4]

STEPS INVOLVED IN PASS:

Step I: navigation of the PASS online web page:

If you enter the words "PASS prediction" in any of the web browsers they allow the direct access to the PASS online website. A free registration can be done and after logging in you can use the prediction page of the online program for prediction of compounds of your interest.

Step II: Drawing the structure of molecule:

PASS online prediction tool uses the 2D structure of the compounds, which forms the basis for the prediction as an input hence the structure can be drawn using chemsketch version 12 and uploaded in the PASS website as a (*.mol) file or it can be directly drawn on the website using JAVA that uses a drawing program called Marvin Sketch.

Step III: Prediction Output:

The input structure which was drawn in the second step its activities are now compared with the structures with known activities present in the database of the program. Bayesian approach being the principle of estimation, the prediction tool will predict the $P_a:P_i$ ratio of the input substance. The output is given in the form of different biological activities in descending of their probability ratios. ^[5]

USES AND APPLICATIONS OF PASS:

Uses:

The activity spectrum of large number of compounds can be predicted in a very less span of time using a fast processor. This has an advantage over the fact that synthesis of compounds takes years and further process in development take more months or years. Hence this will speed up the development process of drugs.

Revealing newer effects of drug substances:

There exist many newer and unknown effects of some drug molecules which can be easily found out using the PASS prediction tool. For instance taking the example of cavinton (vincopetin), the well known activities of the drug is its vasodilatory and spasmolytic effects.

By using PASS prediction, the new activities found for cavinton are Antihypoxic, lipid peroxidise inhibitor, cognition disorders treatment, antischemic, acute neurological disorders etc for which also the drug can be used.

Searching for the new potential leads of drug molecules

If list of desirable and undesirable activities of a particular drug is known, one can easily select such structures from the information already present in the database of the program. Compounds with same dual actions in the database can also be easily known and further studies can be carried out.

Choosing one among several for screening purpose:

PASS aids in selecting the most prospective and most suitable compound among the group for screening of the compounds.

Determining the most relevant screens:

After the compounds are selected for screening, the drug molecules with more relevant screened output among others can be determined based on descending order of difference (Pa-Pi).^[6]

APPLICATIONS:**Major Application Areas:****New indications for old drugs:**

Old drugs or drugs which are continuously used for the one same purpose can have new indications. Finding new indications for old drugs is simpler than discovery of new drugs, this fact has been in focus in the recent years in the research and science field. PASS online program is one of the most suitable tool for predicting new indications for old drugs in a easier way by unexpected or as beneficial side effects. Some of the examples of new indications for old drugs are given below.^[7]

Table no.1: List of new indications for old drugs.

Drug	Initial indication	New indication
Acetyl salicylic acid	Analgesic	Antiplatelet
Allopurinol	Cancer	Gout
Amantidine	Antiviral	Parkinsons disease
Arsenic	Syphilis	Leukaemia
Atomoxetine	Antidepressant	Hyperactivity disorder

Pharmaceuticals Withdrawn from clinical trials and from market:

Various drugs are withdrawn from different phases of clinical trials and also from market for various reasons of risk to patients and severe adverse effects. This results in high economical loss as well as prolonging the development time for the drug. PASS tool is of high benefit here that it predicts the activity of the drug substances even before it is synthesised and chemically analysed. Some examples of withdrawals are listed below.^[8]

Table no.2: List of significant withdrawals.

Drug	withdrawn	Reason
Amoproxon	1970	dermatologic and Ophthalmic toxicity
Benzarone	1992	Hepatitis.
Clomacron	1982	Hepatotoxicity.
Ibufenac	1968	Hepatotoxicity and Jaundice
Ketorolac	1993	Hemorrhage, renal Failure

OTHER TOOLS USED IN COMPUTER AIDED PREDICTION:

1. Swiss target prediction:

It utilises combination of 2D and 3D structure mainly used for prediction of small molecules.^[9]

2. GUSAR online prediction:

It is used in the prediction of structure-activity relationships.^[10]

3. Hit pick target prediction:

It involves chemical screening of compounds and predicting their molecular targets.^[11]

Literature survey revealed that PASS online programme methods were reported ^[12-21]. The aim of the study to bring awareness about online predication tool in the field of research.

CONCLUSION

PASS online prediction tool is successfully used in prediction of activity spectra of substances based on the 2D structures of the biologically active compounds. It allows predicting the biological activity of the drug substances before its synthesis by just using the structure of the compound, according to the principle that the activity spectra of the compound equates its structure. On the basis of computer prediction of biological activity by PASS, several promising activities of different compounds has been introduced in the medicinal fields. New indications of the old drugs can be predicted using pass which can predict over 4000 different kinds of biological activities in few simple steps. It is an easy to use, time saving and economic friendly tool in the area of prediction. In testing of chemical compounds in drug research and development many projects fail because serious adverse effects and toxicity are discovered too late and many existing prospective activities remain unstudied, this can be resolved using pass online prediction which may result in much better results in less time with a mean accuracy of about 95%. PASS has been well accepted by its users in the community, and is now actively used in the field of medicinal chemistry, by both academic organizations and pharma companies.

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